

Input/output Functions of Transient-Evoked Otoacoustic Emission Measured Using Nonlinear Extraction Method

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Abstract. Otoacoustic emissions are generated by two fundamental mechanisms: nonlinear distortion and linear reflection. Abdala and Kalluri [1] suggested combining information from two different types of otoacoustic emissions (OAEs), each generated by a different mechanism, to "characterize sensory hearing loss most effectively". They used stimulus-frequency OAE (SFOAE) generated mainly by linear reflection from irregularities, and distortion-product OAE (DPOAE) whose primary source is nonlinear distortion. Transient-evoked OAE (TEOAE) is another type of reflection source OAEs and we aim to investigate whether this type of OAE could be used in the joint OAE profile instead of SFOAEs. We employed a nonlinear cochlear model to compare I/O functions of click-evoked OAEs (CEOAEs) simulated with the linear extraction method, which requires the use of a suitable window to remove the evoking click, and nonlinear extraction method, which removes the click by subtracting the click response from the scaled response evoked with a click of higher intensity. Despite the fact that the nonlinear method removes everything that grows linearly, the amplitude of simulated CEOAE I/O functions saturated at roughly the same stimulus levels for compressors 6 and 9.54 dB above the probe level. The amplitude fine structure and phase slope of CEOAEs were qualitatively equivalent for both extraction methods. We found qualitatively similar results in measured CEOAEs.

INTRODUCTION

Kemp [2] observed that a transient stimulus presented into the ear canal evokes a response that was diminished or absent in the ears with hearing impairment. The response was later given the name otoacoustic emission (OAE). It was suggested that OAEs evoked with a transient stimulus are primarily generated by the mechanism of linear reflection [3, 4]. Kalluri and Shera [5] showed near equivalence between click-evoked OAEs (CEOAEs) and OAEs evoked with a single tone called stimulus frequency OAEs (SFOAEs), which share a linear reflection generation mechanism. SFOAEs are currently used in the so-called joint reflection-distortion OAE profile developed for diagnostic purposes [1, 6].

Pacecho et al. [7] presented a joint OAE profile in which CEOAEs were used as the OAE type which is evoked due to reflection. They measured CEOAEs using the linear extraction method, which involves using a window to remove clicks from the measured responses. The window also eliminates CEOAEs with very short latencies. In contrast, the nonlinear extraction method subtracts (after rescaling) the CEOAEs measured at slightly different intensities (e.g. about 9 dB) in order to eliminate linearly growing click response.

In this paper, we use a nonlinear cochlear model to compare CEOAEs simulated using the linear extraction method and the nonlinear extraction method. In addition to simulations, we present results measured in one subject.

METHODS

Simulations

We used a nonlinear hydrodynamical model of the cochlea to derive CEOAEs. The model is the same as the model used in [8], please see that paper for its description. We scaled the spatial function $u(x)$ controlling the cochlear amplifier gain in the model in order to create three variants of the model with different gains. At the model section tuned to 1.7 kHz, the gain was set at: 47, 38, and 29 dB. CEOAEs were derived from the model by numerically solving equations in the time domain. We used the Dormand-Prince method, which is a member of the Runge-Kutta family of ODE solvers. We divided the BM into 800 segments and used a sampling frequency of 600 kHz. We used an ideal click as an evoking stimulus (see Fig. 1B in [8]). To simulate the linear extraction method for CEOAEs, we subtracted the model response to a click for a smooth cochlear model from the model response to a click for a cochlear model with roughness in the spatial function $u(x)$ controlling amplification in the model. In addition, we simulated the nonlinear extraction method by rescaling the model response to a click 9 dB above the probe level and subtracting it from the response at the probe level.

Experiments

CEOAEs were measured in eight normally hearing subjects. Here we show results for one subject because of page limit, but the results for other subjects were qualitatively similar. The click design was inspired by the method presented in Goodman et al. [9]. Clicks were generated from the impulse response of a bandpass FIR filter with cutoff frequencies 400 Hz and 4 kHz. For the measurement, we used an ER-10C OAE probe. To remove the probe speaker response from the click, we employed an inverse filtering technique [9, 10].

During the measurement, a click train was made of 228 clicks and presented into the ear repeatedly (in most cases 12 repetitions leading to 2736 clicks were used). The click train was made by repeatedly presenting three clicks with a probe intensity, which were followed by a fourth click with a three times larger amplitude (about 9.54 dB larger than the probe intensity). CEOAEs extracted using the linear method were calculated by averaging the recorded responses to the click at the probe intensity. CEOAEs extracted using the nonlinear method were calculated by summing the responses to the probe clicks and subtracting the responses to the three times larger clicks. Then the resulting CEOAE amplitude in the case of the nonlinear method was divided by three to be comparable in amplitude with the linear method. A 20th-order, 20-ms long recursive exponential window [5] centered 12.5 ms after the center of the recorded click was used to extract the CEOAE and at the same time suppress the click from the response. We used the window even for the nonlinear method because we only focused on low frequencies (up to 4 kHz) in the experiments. In addition, to reduce the background noise, short latency components of OAEs due to click or middle ear ringing, and very long latency components due to synchronized OAEs, time-filtering using a continuous wavelet transform was applied on the averaged CEOAE time domain signal [11, 12]. Specifically, we constructed frequency-dependent recursive exponential windows to extract only those components in the time-frequency domain with latency between two hyperbolic functions given by

$$\tau(f) = a \left[\frac{f}{1 \text{ kHz}} \right]^{-b}, \quad (1)$$

where $b = 0.8$. The shortest latency was yielded by $a = 5$ ms and the longest latency by $a = 17$ ms.

In addition to CEOAEs, we measured swept sine DPOAEs using the method presented in [13], which we slightly adapted. The stimuli were swept with a speed of 2 oct/sec, f_2 was changed between 500 Hz and 8 kHz, $f_2/f_1 = 1.2$, and $L_1 = 0.4L_2 + 39$ dB FPL. To extract the nonlinear distortion component of DPOAEs, we used time-frequency filtering with continuous wavelet transform and extracted the short-latency components with latencies between two hyperbolic functions given by Eq. (1) for $a = 5$ ms and $a = -5$ ms.

RESULTS

Simulated CEOAEs

Figure 1 shows the amplitude and phase of CEOAEs simulated by an ideal click. The left panel presents CEOAEs simulated using the linear extraction method and the right panel presents CEOAEs simulated using the nonlinear extraction method for 9 dB criteria. Regardless of the extraction method, the CEOAE amplitude increases with increasing stimulus intensity until it saturates. Amplitude fine-structure and phase of CEOAEs are near-level invariant. In addition, there seems to be almost no difference between the CEOAE amplitude fine structure and phase slope for the linear and nonlinear extraction methods. The simulated nonlinear CEOAE amplitude does grow faster, but the amplitudes are also considerably smaller for the nonlinear method. Cochlear amplification affects CEOAE amplitude and phase curvature.

FIGURE 1. Amplitude and phase of CEOAE derived from the cochlear model with various gains (indicated above each graph). Each line depicts CEOAEs for different click levels ranging between 70 to 124 dB re $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ a.u. in 6-dB steps. CEOAEs extracted by the nonlinear extraction method use the click response 9 dB above the probe intensity. Left: Linear extraction method. Right: Nonlinear extraction method for 9-dB criteria. Notice the near equivalence of amplitude fine structure and phase slope between linear and nonlinear methods. However, in case of the nonlinear method, the amplitude increases faster than for the linear method.

In Fig. 2, the I/O functions of simulated CEOAEs at 1720 Hz are shown. At this frequency, the amplitude fine structure is at a local maximum at the lowest stimulus intensity; see the vertical black dashed line in Fig. 1. We can see that the nonlinear extraction method yields CEOAEs with a significantly lower amplitude and more importantly, with strongly different growth; i.e. cubic growth at the lowest intensities in contrast to the linear growth for the linear extraction method. For comparison between the linear and the nonlinear extraction methods, the important information is whether the I/O functions or transfer functions can be characterized by several parameters used in joint OAE profile [1, 14]. For example, in the SFOAE transfer function, we can detect the maximal value of the transfer function called "peak strength", then the point where the emission strength begins to decrease called "compression threshold" and the slope of the transfer function at large intensities called "compression slope" [1]. If we define the compression threshold as the stimulus level for which the I/O function slope halves then it is almost at the same intensities for the linear extraction and the nonlinear extraction methods (see Fig. 2A,C). Similar compression thresholds can be estimated by the transfer functions (Fig. 2B). However, because the transfer function for the nonlinear method has a maximum near the compression threshold for the linear method, we decided to detect this maximum as the compression threshold. In addition to the compression threshold, compression slopes are also very similar if we compare linear extraction and nonlinear extraction methods.

The I/O functions obtained using the model with different gains of the cochlear amplifier show that the gain affects the CEOAE amplitude (higher gain yields higher amplitude) and intensity for which the I/O functions saturate and the compression thresholds shift towards larger intensities as the gain decreases. At the lowest intensities, for the linear extraction method, the CEOAE amplitude declines by about the same amount as the amplifier gain. In contrast, the decline is much larger for the nonlinear extraction method. However, because the compression threshold shifts

FIGURE 2. A: I/O functions of CEOAEs shown in Fig. 1, where the frequency 1720 Hz is indicated with vertical black dashed line. The color of lines indicate the extraction method (black - linear method, red - nonlinear method for 9 dB criteria, blue - nonlinear method for 6 dB criteria) and the line style indicates model gain: 48 dB (solid line), 37 dB (dotted line), and 29 dB (dashed line). B: CEOAE transfer function, i.e. an I/O function after subtraction of the stimulus level. C: Numerically derived I/O functions along the stimulus level shown in panel A. The markers in A and C indicate the levels for which the slope of the I/O functions is half of the highest slope (compression threshold); i.e. 0.5 for the linearly growing I/O functions simulated using linear extraction method and 1.5 for the I/O function simulated using nonlinear extraction methods. We used point 1.5 for the 6 dB criteria too although the I/O function is changing the slope at the lowest intensities. Notice that the compression thresholds from the I/O functions are almost equivalent for linear and nonlinear methods. D: The numerical derivative (with respect to stimulus level) of the CEOAE gain functions shown in panel B. The unfilled markers indicate points where the derivative of the gain functions is half the value at the lowest intensities. Additionally, for the nonlinear extraction method, the filled markers indicate the level where the derivative is zero; i.e. the maximum of the gain function. Such defined compression thresholds are approximately at the same levels.

towards higher intensities as the gain decreases, the highest CEOAE amplitudes are much less affected by the cochlear amplifier gain. Its effect seems to be similar for the linear and the nonlinear extraction methods.

The main outcomes of the presented simulations are that CEOAE amplitude saturates as the click intensity grows whereas the phase slope is relatively level invariant. These simulation results agree with measured CEOAE gains presented in Kalluri and Shera [5] (see, e.g., their Figs 3(A) and 6). At the highest intensities, they estimated the slope of the gain function to be about -0.8. The value of -1 would indicate complete saturation of the I/O response.

Measured CEOAEs

Figure 3 shows the amplitude and phase of CEOAEs recorded in the left ear of subject s003. The left panel shows CEOAEs measured using linear extraction method and the right panel shows CEOAEs measured using nonlinear extraction method. Measured CEOAEs indicate agreement between simulated CEOAEs (Fig. 1) in that the amplitude fine-structure and phase slope is near equivalent for the linear extraction method and the nonlinear extraction method.

Figure 4 shows the transfer functions of CEOAEs presented in Fig. 3 and DPOAE transfer functions measured in

the same subject at the same f_2 value as the CEOAE frequency. The CEOAE transfer functions qualitatively agree with simulations (Fig. 2,B), however, in the experiment we are covering much smaller dynamic range (less than 30 dB). Comparison with DPOAEs indicates that the compression thresholds for DPOAEs would be much lower than compression thresholds for CEOAEs, which contrasts to SFOAE and DPOAE compression thresholds presented for normal hearing subjects [14].

FIGURE 3. Amplitude and phase of CEOAEs measured in subject s003 (left ear). The legend indicates click intensities in dB peSPL. The extraction method is written above each panel. Notice the similarities between the amplitude fine structure and phase slope. Also notice the near level invariance of the phase slope and saturation of the CEOAE amplitude at the highest intensities.

FIGURE 4. CEOAE transfer functions measured at 0.8, 1.6, and 2.08 kHz (indicated above each graph and shown by vertical dashed lines in Fig. 3) and DPOAE transfer functions measured at f_2 values equal to the chosen CEOAE frequencies. The transfer functions were obtained by dividing the CEOAEs by the spectrum of the click recorded in the ear canal [5]. Transfer functions measured using the linear method are in the legend indicated by "Lin" and the transfer functions measured using the nonlinear method by "NL". The gray dashed line has a slope of -1, which indicates the maximal slope observed in simulated transfer functions (Fig. 2B,D).

CONCLUSION

CEOAEs simulated using the linear extraction method and the nonlinear extraction method have very similar amplitude fine structure and phase slope. In addition, the I/O functions or CEOAE transfer functions can be used to extract important parameters for joint OAE profile: compression threshold, compression slope, and peak strength. The first two parameters are relatively equivalent for the linear extraction method and the nonlinear extraction method. CEOAEs recorded in normally hearing subjects show qualitative agreement with simulated CEOAEs.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[William Salloom]: Interesting paper and concept of study. I attached a detailed review of the paper with comments.

[Václav Vencovský]: Thank you Will. We have implemented your comments during revision.

[William Salloom]: One question I have is regarding the nonlinear extraction method. It seems in both the simulation and measured CEOAE responses that the nonlinear method underestimates the amplitude compared to the linear method responses, at least at the lower click levels tested. What do you suspect is causing this difference?

[Václav Vencovský]: The nonlinear method shows only the part of CEOAE that grows nonlinearly with stimulus intensity. In other words, we subtract the linearly growing part of the emission out therefore the final amplitude is smaller than in case of the linear method.

[William Salloom]: It seems that there may be a practical significance to using CEOAEs over SFOAEs, in terms of analysis and the type of stimuli used. Is that the reason behind trying use the CEOAEs in lieu of SFOAEs?

[Václav Vencovský]: There is more reasons why we decided to explore CEOAEs. The main one is purely practical because we have started measurements in a hospital where we use already implemented CEOAE measurement system. At the same time, we are curious to compare our CEOAEs for various click levels with SFOAEs presented by other studies.